

D6.1 – REPORT ON DEFINITION OF KPIS FOR DEMONSTRATORS

Project 101091536

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D6.1 – Report on Definition of KPIs for Demonstrators

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
MU	Masaryk University
KTH	Kungliga Tekniska Högskolan
TUC	Technical University of Chemnitz
ULFS	University of Ljubljana
IDE	IDENER Research & Development AIE
IRIS	IRIS Technology Solutions
SIG	Signifikant Svenska AB
C-ECO	Circular Economy Solutions GmbH
GOR	Gorenje gospodinjski aparati, d.o.o.
ARC	Arcelik
LEX	Lexmark
CHX	Crowdhelix
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader
DiCiM	Digitalised Value Management for unlocking the potential of the Circular Manufacturing Systems with integrated digital solutions
D	Deliverable
BO	Business Objective
WEEE	Waste of Electric and Electronic Equipment
PCB	Printed Circuit Board
FTE	Full Time Equivalent
CMS	Circular Manufacturing Systems
DOA	Description of Action
N/A	Not applicable
AR	Augmented Reality
ML	Machine Learning
AI	Artificial Intelligence
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer
IoT	Internet of Things
MPS	Managed Print Services
RLC	Reverse Logistics Centre
eq.	Equivalent

No.	Number
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TBL	Triple Bottom Line
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
PSS	Product Service System
RFID	Radio Frequency Identification
CE	Circular Economy
CMS	Circular Manufacturing Systems

1. Executive Summary

The primary challenge addressed by this deliverable is the identification of effective and measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) capable of quantifying and evaluating the impacts arising from the integration of digital technologies developed under the DiCiM project. This identification process is critical for aligning technological advancements with the strategic business objectives of the project's four demonstrators: Arcelik (ARC), Gorenje (GOR), Lexmark (LEX) and Circular Economy Solutions GmbH (C-ECO).

The report aims to present a comprehensive set of measurable KPIs designed to assess the socio-economic and environmental impacts facilitated by the project's digital technological innovations. These indicators are crucial for enabling demonstrators to accurately measure their progress and success in achieving predefined business objectives and enhancing overall operational performance.

To achieve these objectives, this deliverable employs a structured two-stage methodology. Initially, a top-down approach is utilized, involving a detailed literature review of scientific articles sourced from the Scopus database. This literature review is essential for identifying relevant KPIs previously employed in assessing the impacts of digital technologies, particularly focusing on economic viability, social impact, and environmental sustainability. Subsequently, a bottom-up approach is adopted through co-creation workshops conducted in collaboration with demonstrators, aimed at developing customized, practical, and actionable KPIs directly tied to each demonstrator's unique business objectives and technological context(s).

The core of this deliverable lies in bridging the gap between technological advancements and tangible business impacts. It emphasizes providing demonstrators with precise, relevant, and quantifiable KPIs, which directly reflect the outcomes derived from the DiCiM project's digital innovations.

The deliverable scope encompasses the development and detailed elaboration of measurable KPIs closely aligned with business objectives previously established in deliverable D1.2, while simultaneously incorporating technical specifications delineated in deliverable D1.1. This ensures a coherent and integrated approach to KPI formulation, leveraging insights and groundwork laid by previous project milestones.

This deliverable serves as a crucial bridge linking past and future project developments. It is fundamentally built upon previous deliverables (D1.1 and D1.2), leveraging established business objectives and technical requirements as foundational inputs. Moreover, it lays a robust foundation for subsequent phases of the project, specifically for deliverables D6.2, D6.3, and D6.4. Deliverable D6.2 will establish baseline measures and evaluate the feasibility and impact of these KPIs. Deliverable D6.3 will subsequently assess the commercial viability and potential for scale-up at the demonstrator level, and deliverable D6.4 will explore scalability and impact potential at the broader sector level.

Ultimately, this report provides demonstrators with a strategic framework for systematically tracking and evaluating the socio-economic and environmental impacts of integrating state-of-the-art digital technologies. By clearly defining and implementing measurable KPIs, this deliverable empowers demonstrators to monitor ongoing progress, optimize performance, and effectively demonstrate the value generated through their technological and business innovations.

2. Introduction and Objectives

The manufacturing industry is currently undergoing a significant transformation characterized by a "twin transition." On one hand, Industry 4.0, driven by digitalization and state-of-the-art digital technologies, is fundamentally reshaping manufacturing processes and systems (Rüßmanns et al., 2015). Concurrently, the European manufacturing sector is also actively transitioning toward greater sustainability, marked by efforts to reduce emissions, enhance social responsibility, and ensure profitability (European Commission, 2019). In this context, the circular economy has emerged as a prominent area of research and practice, providing viable strategies to achieve sustainability objectives across environmental, social, and economic domains.

Within this dual transition towards sustainability and increased digital capabilities, Circular Manufacturing Systems (CMS) have emerged as a pivotal concept, garnering substantial attention from both industry practitioners and academic researchers (Asif and M, 2017; Rashid et al., 2020). There is a growing consensus in academia and practice acknowledging digitalization as a crucial enabler of sustainability and circular economy principles within the manufacturing sector (Bag et al., 2021; Chauhan et al., 2022; Neri et al., 2025).

Building on this recognition, recent studies, such as that by Sahoo and Upadhyay (2024), emphasize the necessity of developing tailored Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) specifically designed to measure the environmental, economic, and social impacts of circular economy initiatives. Despite acknowledging the importance of such tailored KPIs, the existing research lacks substantial empirical assessment and benchmarking of these indicators. Addressing this gap through the creation of robust, context-specific KPIs is essential for accurately capturing and assessing the effectiveness of digital technology integration, facilitating continuous improvement across sustainability's triple bottom line, and comprehensively understanding the true impact of digital technologies in this context.

In essence, KPIs serve as critical tools for organizations to evaluate progress toward their strategic business objectives. *Defined as measurable values, KPIs quantify and assess the impact and performance relative to predefined business goals, providing clarity on how effectively these objectives are being met.* Particularly within digitalization contexts, KPIs become indispensable, offering precise measurements that elucidate the extent to which specific goals, such as efficiency improvements or enhanced sustainability impacts, have been realized.

Effective KPIs possess several essential characteristics: they must be relevant, quantifiable, and actionable. Relevance ensures that each KPI aligns directly with specific organizational objectives and contexts. Quantifiability provides an objective basis for performance evaluation, eliminating ambiguity. Actionability means KPIs directly inform strategic and operational decision-making processes, guiding corrective actions and enabling continuous improvement. Additionally, KPIs must be meticulously tailored to reflect specific organizational and manufacturing objectives to ensure practical relevance and effectiveness.

Furthermore, as emphasized by (Hester et al., 2017), the scientific grounding of KPIs is critical, ensuring that these metrics are based on stakeholder's business objectives and produce measurable outcomes that accurately reflect organizational performance. Such a scientifically validated approach enhances the credibility and utility of KPIs, thereby enabling robust performance monitoring, effective reporting, and informed decision-making.

With the intention of creating context-specific and decisive KPIs, there is a strong emphasis on adopting a bottom-up approach, facilitated through co-creation workshops involving demonstrators. These workshops allow for brainstorming and collaborative identification and definition of KPIs that reflect the outcomes of demonstrators' specific business objectives. Consequently, a well-defined methodology is adopted, utilizing previous DiCiM developments as reference points. Specifically, this involves scanning demonstrators' business objectives as established in deliverable D1.2, alongside technical specifications and development features outlined in deliverable D1.1.

Additionally, to capture state-of-the-art developments and recent advances in scientific research, a comprehensive literature review is conducted. This literature review provides an extensive list of KPIs discussed in existing research, which are specifically designed to measure the impacts of digitalization technologies within circular manufacturing systems.

The remainder of this report is structured as follows: Chapter 3 presents the detailed methodology adopted, Chapter 4 provides a comprehensive list of KPI's derived from the literature review i.e. top-down approach, Chapter 5 identifies and defines measurable KPIs applicable to all four demonstrators, leveraging the bottom-up methodology. Finally, Chapter 6 concludes the report by outlining future directions for subsequent work in Work Package 6, along with discussing the broader implications of this study.

3. Methodology

3.1. Literature Review - The top-down approach

A structured two-phase methodological approach is employed to identify and define measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for evaluating the socio-economic and environmental impacts of digital technologies within circular economy contexts in the manufacturing sector. The two phases, conducted concurrently, are a systematic literature review of peer-reviewed academic publications and a series of co-creation workshops involving project demonstrators.

The first phase involves conducting a literature review utilizing the Scopus database, chosen due to its comprehensive coverage of peer-reviewed academic literature relevant to the topics under study. The objective of this review is to identify existing KPIs and their application in assessing the impacts of digital technologies specifically within circular manufacturing systems, emphasizing economic, environmental, and social dimensions.

To achieve comprehensive and relevant coverage, specific search criteria and key terms were developed, structured, and clustered into four major thematic categories: circular economy terms, performance measurement terms, manufacturing terms, and digital technology terms.

Initial search key included only “circular economy” and “circular manufacturing”. However, the keyword “remanufacturing” was appended to the search query on reviewing keywords of first 10 pages of google scholar. The performance measurement keywords adopted are justified by the “triple bottom line” keywords and the 3 components of “social”, “economic” and “environmental” aspects. To narrow down the search query particular to DiCiM project partners, they key words “manufact*” and “production” was utilized. Finally, the objective of DiCiM project focuses on unlocking the value of digital technologies. Hence a combination of Industry 4.0 based technologies was utilized to define the search query on Scopus databases. The search query employed is presented in Table 1:

Table 1: Keywords used for literature review

Circular Terms	Economy	Performance Measurement Terms	Manufacturing Terms	Digitalization Terms
Circular economy, Circular manufacturing, Remanufacturing		KPI, Performance, Measur*, Key performance indicat*, Triple bottom line, TBL, Economic impact, Economic performance, Environmental impact, Environmental performance, Social impact, Social performance	Manufact*, Production	Digitalization, Digital transformation, Industry 4.0, Cyber-physical systems, IoT, Internet of things, Artificial intelligence, AI, Machine learning, ML, Big data, Data analytics, Blockchain, Digital twin, Cloud computing, Augmented reality, Virtual reality

Articles were selected based on clearly defined criteria, ensuring quality, relevance, and comprehensiveness:

1. Source type: Peer-reviewed journals, conference articles, book chapters, and review articles from the Scopus database.
2. Language: English.
3. Publication period: Publications from 2013 onwards to ensure currency and relevance given the rapid development in digital technologies ensuring comprehensive coverage.

Initially, 652 articles were retrieved based on these criteria. These articles underwent a rigorous preliminary selection based on titles, abstracts, and keywords, aimed at confirming thematic relevance to circular economy applications and the digital technologies defined above. After this initial screening, 179 articles were shortlisted for a more detailed assessment of titles and abstracts.

Following this stage, a detailed full-text assessment was conducted to ensure compliance with four essential inclusion criteria:

1. Clear relevance to digitalization technologies outlined in the search keywords.

2. Direct application or relevance to circular manufacturing systems and processes.
3. Explicit information addressing socio-economic and environmental impacts.
4. Availability of robust empirical data or clearly outlined theoretical frameworks for KPI measurement.

After applying these rigorous selection criteria, a final set of 12 articles was considered for comprehensive review. This final dataset provides a solid foundation for identifying existing KPIs and the impact of digitalization within circular manufacturing contexts, thereby serving as a benchmark and reference point for developing further KPIs. The snowballing techniques based on the reference of selected articles was used to identify KPIs.

Following the literature review, it became evident that the identified KPIs from existing literature provided generic insights and lacked specificity and applicability across all demonstrators. Thus, the need emerged to adopt a complementary bottom-up approach for more context-specific, demonstrator-tailored KPIs.

3.2. Co-creation Workshops - The bottom-up approach

For the bottom-up approach, the first step involved a detailed analysis of deliverables D1.1 and D1.2, which laid foundational knowledge about technological features and business objectives defined within the DiCiM project. This step was essential for aligning DiCiM's technological developments with demonstrators' strategic business objectives.

Following the initial mapping, the co-creation workshop was designed through careful formulation of open-ended yet guided questions. These questions aimed at eliciting detailed insights from demonstrators regarding their expectations, capabilities, and specific KPI needs related to their business objectives.

After finalizing the workshop design, all four demonstrators (ARC, GOR, LEX and C-ECO) were invited to a preliminary plenary session. Each demonstrator participated in a 45-minute introductory meeting, where they were briefed thoroughly on the workshop objectives, expectations, necessary preparations, and the overall design and structure of the upcoming workshops.

Given the diverse and specific business requirements of each project partner, an iterative process was adopted for the co-creation workshops. The workshops were structured systematically, following clear and methodical steps:

Initially, demonstrators revisited and evaluated the KPIs listed in the Description of Action (DOA) for relevance and applicability. This is documented in Annex B. Subsequently, business objectives outlined in deliverable D1.2 were reviewed to set clear goals for measuring the impacts of digital technologies. A structured template was created to systematically document the economic, environmental, and social impacts of digital technologies on each business objective.

During this process, demonstrators identified whether they already measured each business objective and if the relevant data were available. If insufficient data existed, steps were defined to acquire necessary data. Demonstrators then articulated the processes and underlying philosophy for each business objective, considering the potential need for multiple KPIs to effectively capture comprehensive impacts. This iterative assessment continued systematically for each KPI across all identified business objectives until completion.

During the process, several KPIs initially proposed in the Description of Action (DoA) were identified too generic or lacking sufficient relevance in measuring the targeted business objectives. These KPIs were subsequently converted to more appropriate indicators that more accurately capture the impact and performance related to the business goals. These comprehensive KPIs were thus selected to enable informed decision-making and to facilitate effective tracking of progress.

This iterative bottom-up approach ensures that KPIs are precisely aligned with demonstrators' specific business needs, enhancing practical applicability and effectiveness in measuring digitalization impacts. The design and flow of workshop is presented in a flowchart detailed in Figure 1. Annex A further details the structure of workshop for LEX as an example. Consistent design of workshop is maintained for the remaining 3 demonstrators.

Figure 1: Workshop design for bottom-up approach

The outcomes of both methodological phases—the top-down literature review and the bottom-up co-creation workshops—are integrated within this report, ensuring that the identified KPIs are robust, context-specific, and grounded in both scientific literature and practical applicability. This comprehensive methodological framework thus supports demonstrators in effectively tracking, measuring, and evaluating the socio-economic and environmental impacts of digital technology implementations within their business contexts. The complete research design described above is visually represented in the methodological flowchart provided in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Research Design

4. Results

This chapter presents the outcomes derived from the two-phase methodological framework outlined in Chapter 3, clearly illustrating the diversity and specificity of KPIs identified from both the systematic literature review (top-down approach) and co-creation workshops with the project's demonstrators (bottom-up approach). The results aim to highlight the potential KPIs available in existing scholarly literature and the tailored KPIs specifically formulated in alignment with demonstrators' strategic business objectives.

The subsequent subchapters (4.2 to 4.5) detail the KPIs specifically derived through the bottom-up co-creation workshops for each of the project demonstrators: Arcelik (ARC), Gorenje (GOR), Lexmark (LEX) and Circular Economy Solutions GmbH (C-ECO). Each subchapter begins by introducing the specific demonstrator's business objectives and subsequently presents the finalized set of measurable KPIs identified for task 6.2 of the DiCiM project. These KPIs were selected based on their direct alignment with demonstrators' unique business logic, requirements, and strategic goals, thus ensuring robust and practical impact assessment.

Specifically:

- Subchapter 4.2: Arcelik (ARC)
- Subchapter 4.3: Gorenje (GOR)
- Subchapter 4.4: Lexmark (LEX)
- Subchapter 4.5: Circular Economy GmbH (C-ECO)

For each demonstrator, the KPIs reflect tailored measurement strategies optimized to evaluate the socio-economic and environmental performance accurately and effectively. Each of these subchapters for demonstrators include the following subchapters

1. Creation of tailored KPI(s) for each business objectives for each demonstrator
2. Providing a short description of each KPI
3. Linking the economic, environmental and social implication of the created KPIs

4.1. KPIs Derived from Literature Review

Subchapter 4.1 provides a comprehensive summary of KPIs obtained through an extensive literature review and subsequent snowballing method. The identified KPIs are systematically categorized under three core themes: Economic impact KPIs, Social impact KPIs, and Environmental impact KPIs. This categorization provides a structured overview of existing measurable indicators discussed across scholarly articles, thus offering a broad perspective on potential KPIs relevant to circular manufacturing systems enabled by digital technologies.

Economic impact KPIs:

- **Operational productivity:** output per unit of input (e.g., value-added or units per labour-hour) improved through digitally enabled circular processes (Kristoffersen et al., 2020; Luciano et al., 2021; Moreno et al., 2019)
- **Production / operating cost:** total monetary cost of producing goods or running processes; digital tools can cut costs or raise them via new investment (Khan et al., 2022b; Khan et al., 2022a; Abdul-Hamid et al., 2020; Atif et al., 2021)
- **Transport cost:** direct logistics expenditure that falls when routing and loading are digitally optimised (Bressanelli et al., 2022; Ajwani-Ramchandani et al., 2021; Vaccaro and Buoninconti, 2021; de Mattos Nascimento et al., 2022)
- **Production speed:** cycle-time or throughput of manufacturing lines accelerated by digital control systems (Faria et al., 2020; García-Muiña et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022b; Khan et al., 2022a; Abdul-Hamid et al., 2020; Atif et al., 2021)
- **Process error rate / accuracy:** percentage of defects or rework; advanced analytics and IoT reduce errors and raise accuracy (Abdul-Hamid et al., 2020; Alves et al., 2022; Atif et al., 2021; Bag et al., 2020a; Bag et al., 2020b; Bag et al., 2021; Bressanelli et al., 2022; Krstić et al., 2022; Magrini et al., 2021; Rejeb et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2022)
- **Supply-chain flexibility:** ability to meet variable demand quickly (often measured as lead time); enhanced by real-time data sharing (Khan et al., 2022b; Khan et al., 2022a; Abdul-Hamid et al., 2020; Atif et al., 2021)
- **Competitiveness:** market-oriented metrics such as revenue growth or share that improve when digital circular strategies strengthen differentiation (Cerreta et al., 2020)

- **Decision-making efficiency:** time or iterations required for operational decisions; shortened by data-driven insights (Bressanelli et al., 2022; Del Giudice et al., 2020; de Souza et al., 2021; Khan et al., 2022a)
- **Digitalisation cost increase:** additional capital or operating outlay incurred when adopting Industry 4.0 tools for circularity (Di Maria et al., 2023)
- **Cost savings:** monetary reductions achieved via resource-efficient, digitally monitored circular operations (Sassanelli & Terzi 2023)
- **Resource efficiency:** extent to which inputs are optimally utilised through data-driven circular practices (Sassanelli & Terzi 2023)
- **Reduced operational risk:** fall in business risk exposure achieved through digitally enabled circular methods (Sassanelli & Terzi 2023)
- **Take back cost:** Measures the cost of collecting used products from customers. Includes reverse logistics and customer participation (Imtavanich and Gupta, 2006).
- **Total sorting cost:** Measures the total cost of sorting components or materials for recycling, recovery, or disposal (Vadde et al., 2011).
- **Inventory holding cost:** Represents the total cost of storing inventory, including warehousing, insurance, and depreciation (Imtavanich and Gupta, 2006).
- **Cost of disassembly:** Measures the cost to disassemble a product into components without causing damage. Influenced by product complexity and disassembly method (Gupta et al., 2011).
- **Rework cost:** Measures the cost to fix defective products and return them to their original condition. Includes labor and time (Shahbazi et al., 2018).
- **Maintenance revenue:** Revenue generated from offering repairs, upgrades and maintenance (Chou et al., 2015; Feil et al., 2015).
- **Cost of remanufacturing:** Measures the full cost of remanufacturing a product, including disassembly, cleaning, reassembly, and testing (Bressanelli et al., 2024).
- **Transportation operational cost:** sum of variable, fixed and waiting charges for moving goods across truck, rail and ship, monitored through the digital model — (Dev et al., 2020)
- **Secondary revenue:** Revenue from reused, remanufactured and refurbished components and products (Alam et al., 2025).
- **Shortage/back-order cost:** penalty attached to unmet demand when digital coordination fails to balance supply and returns — (Dev et al., 2020)

- **Maintenance revenue:** Revenue generated from offering repairs, upgrades and maintenance (Chou et al., 2015; Feil et al., 2015).
- **R&D & innovation investment ratio:** proportion of total capital expenditure channelled into new R&D or innovation equipment, captured automatically in the ERP, which shows how far digital spending supports circular-economy objectives — (García-Muiña et al., 2021)
- **R&D & innovation workforce share:** percentage of employees assigned to R&D/innovation roles, derived from HR databases, signalling the firm’s commitment to future circular value creation — (García-Muiña et al., 2021)
- **Social Return on Investment (SROI):** efficiency index that monetises the social value created for every euro invested, linking economic resources to wider circular benefits — (Watson et al., 2016)
- **Spare-parts usage:** data-driven maintenance lowers the number of replacement parts consumed per operating hour — (Arioli et al., 2023; Ren et al., 2019)
- **Number of collections:** monthly pick-ups of returned products (Oliveira Neto et al., 2023).
- **Revenue from recyclables:** several digitalised WEEE models report extra income from selling recovered materials (Oliveira Neto et al., 2023).
- **Energy-consumption cost decrease:** evaluates the reduction in energy spending realised through digitally optimised circular operations (Ghaithan et al., 2023)
- **Interoperability:** digitally enabled systems in a circular supply chain can exchange and interpret data without manual intervention — (Hettiarachchi et al., 2022)
- **Added value:** difference between output value and input costs, indicating extra wealth created through digitally enabled, resource-efficient production (Ali et al., 2022).
- **Hourly labour productivity:** output per paid labour-hour, evidencing efficiency gains from smart automation and data-driven control (Ali et al., 2022).
- **Gross operating margin:** operating surplus as a share of income, reflecting profitability improvements from combining Industry 4.0 and environmental assets (Ali et al., 2022).

Environmental impact KPIs

- **Energy consumption:** kilowatt-hours used by production, data centres, IoT devices or blockchain operations — (Magrini et al., 2021; Ajwani-Ramchandani et al., 2021; Moreno et al., 2019; Fraga-Lamas et al., 2021; Hoosain et al., 2020)
- **CO₂ emissions:** tonnes of greenhouse gases released, directly linked to energy use and transport — (Bressanelli et al., 2022; Warmington-Lundström and Laurenti, 2020; Magrini et al., 2021; Moreno et al., 2019; Ajwani-Ramchandani et al., 2021; Vaccaro and Buoninconti, 2021; de Mattos Nascimento et al., 2022; Fraga-Lamas et al., 2021; Hoosain et al., 2020; Townsend and Coroama, 2018; Dominish et al., 2018)
- **Raw / virgin material use:** mass of newly extracted resources entering products; eco-design and additive manufacturing aim to lower this figure — (Bressanelli et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2022; Magrini et al., 2021; Atif et al., 2021; Vaccaro and Buoninconti, 2021; de Mattos Nascimento et al., 2022; Fraga-Lamas et al., 2021; Townsend and Coroama, 2018; Dominish et al., 2018)
- **Consumption of scarce critical materials:** tracking of rare-earths or conflict minerals required for digital devices — (Magrini et al., 2021; Bag et al., 2020b; Fraga-Lamas et al., 2021)
- **Waste Minimization:** total solid waste from production and products (scrap, packaging, etc.) — (Bressanelli et al., 2022; Tang et al., 2022; Magrini et al., 2021; Atif et al., 2021; Vaccaro and Buoninconti, 2021; de Mattos Nascimento et al., 2022; Fraga-Lamas et al., 2021; Hoosain et al., 2020; Condemi et al., 2019; Townsend and Coroama, 2018; Dominish et al., 2018)
- **E-waste volume:** weight of obsolete electronic devices and RFID tags requiring responsible management — (Magrini et al., 2021; Fraga-Lamas et al., 2021; Hoosain et al., 2020; Condemi et al., 2019)
- **Transport emissions:** CO₂ or NO_x produced by logistics fleets; digital route optimisation targets reductions — (Bressanelli et al., 2022; Ajwani-Ramchandani et al., 2021; Vaccaro and Buoninconti, 2021; de Mattos Nascimento et al., 2022)
- **Rebound-effect ratio:** percentage of initial environmental gains offset by higher demand stimulated through efficiency or convenience — (Warmington-Lundström and Laurenti, 2020; Townsend and Coroama, 2018; Dominish et al., 2018)
- **Reduced resource use:** cut in virgin material consumption through digitally steered circular practices — (Khan et al. 2024)
- **Resource reuse rate:** proportion of inputs reused within production thanks to digital tracking — (Khan et al. 2024)

- **Recycling rate:** share of materials recycled, monitored and improved through digital systems — (Khan et al. 2024)
- **Remanufacturing rate:** embedded tracking data raises the proportion of returned products successfully remanufactured — (Fofou et al., 2021; Ren et al., 2019)
- **Resource recovery rate:** percentage of outputs recovered for further use via technology-enabled circular flows — (Khan et al. 2024)
- **Resource regeneration rate:** extent to which resources are regenerated through digitally supported circular loops — (Khan et al. 2024)
- **Waste minimisation:** reduction in waste volumes delivered by data-driven circular processes — (Khan et al. 2024)
- **Lower toxic emissions:** fall in harmful releases attributable to circular models enhanced by digital technologies — (Bahadori, Kaymak & Seraj 2021)
- **Reduction of hazardous:** Lower mass of harmful substances ending up in landfills (Nascimento et al., 2018).
- **Renewable-energy share:** percentage of total power drawn from renewables (Waibel et al., 2017).
- **Scrap rate:** proportion of material scrapped on the shop floor (Felsberger and Reiner, 2020)
- **Water-consumption per product:** litres of freshwater withdrawn to manufacture one unit (Cavaliere et al., 2024)
- **Circular-purchasing rate:** share of input materials that are recycled, remanufactured or readily recyclable (Yu et al., 2022)
- **Component-recovery rate:** percentage of parts successfully reclaimed from end-of-life products via digitally guided disassembly and remanufacturing — (Masi et al., 2017).
- **Export revenue:** value of goods sold internationally, showing the reach that Industry 4.0 gives to circular-economy products (Ali et al., 2022).
- **Product life-cycle extension:** IoT-enabled reuse, refurbish and remanufacture loops lengthen product service life — (Awan et al., 2021)

Social impact KPIs

- **Skill development:** hours of training or certifications achieved by employees moving to digital-circular tasks — (Millard et al., 2018)

- **Jobs created:** net number of new (often higher-skill) positions generated by 3-D printing or data-analytics roles — (Millard et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2023)
- **Jobs displaced:** count of low-skill roles lost or automated as digital tools spread — (Abdul-Hamid et al., 2020)
- **Trust among supply-chain actors:** degree of confidence (survey index or verified transactions) fostered by blockchain traceability — (de Filippi and Carbone, 2021; Di Maria et al., 2023; Ajwani-Ramchandani et al., 2021)
- **Accountability / traceability level:** share of products whose provenance can be tracked end-to-end — (de Filippi and Carbone, 2021; Di Maria et al., 2023; Ajwani-Ramchandani et al., 2021)
- **Communication effectiveness:** frequency or latency of information exchange between partners, improved by real-time platforms — (de Filippi and Carbone, 2021; Di Maria et al., 2023; Ajwani-Ramchandani et al., 2021)
- **Community cohesion:** local collaboration emerging from maker or sharing initiatives (often measured qualitatively) — (Millard et al., 2018)
- **Personal satisfaction:** self-reported well-being of participants in circular activities (e.g., makers or sharers) — (Millard et al., 2018)
- **Employee productivity:** rise in staff output stimulated by digital leadership supporting circular-economy work methods — (Wasono & Furinto 2018)
- **Customer attraction:** ability to draw environmentally conscious consumers through technology-aided circular transparency — (Centobelli et al. 2022)
- **Supply-chain transparency:** improved visibility for stakeholders provided by blockchain in circular supply networks — (Centobelli et al. 2022)
- **Training hours per employee:** Total hours spent on employee skill and capacity development (Ahi and Searcy, 2015; Rahdari and Anvary Rostamy, 2015).
- **FTEs in CE roles:** Number of full-time employees in Circular Economy based operations and roles (Bressanelli et al., 2024).
- **Product take-back offering:** Number of customers offered product take-back contracts (Valenzuela-Venegas et al., 2016).
- **Responsible consumption Outreach:** Number of digital campaigns promoting responsible consumption (Yadav et al., 2020).
- **Work-load balance index:** degree tasks are evenly distributed (Felsberger & Reiner 2020)

- **Safety of employees:** effectiveness of measures protecting worker well-being (Yadav et al., 2020)
- **Improved-employee-health score:** percentage of the workforce reporting better physical well-being (Kamble et al., 2020).
- **Reduced labour claims:** number of workplace compensation or grievance claims filed per year (Kamble et al., 2020).
- **Customer-complaint frequency:** number of quality-related complaints received per 1 000 units sold (Kamble et al., 2020).
- **Stakeholder education on recycling and sustainability:** Outreach activities to customers, suppliers, resellers etc to spread knowledge on sustainability and knowledge transfer (Yadav et al., 2020)
- **Customer satisfaction:** Enhanced consumer satisfaction through improved product quality and eco-friendly design (Yu et al., 2022).
- **Employee improvement suggestion options:** Availability of channels for employees to suggest improvements (Sangwa and Sangwan, 2017)
- **Gender-equality ratio:** share of female employees in the workforce, rated as a social-rate ratio (García-Muiña et al., 2021).
- **Migrant-worker inclusion ratio:** proportion of migrant employees, highlighting diversity and equal-opportunity performance in the digitalised plant (García-Muiña et al., 2021)
- **Training-hours indicator:** average annual training hours per employee, logged automatically and used to measure human-capital development for circular skills (García-Muiña et al., 2021)
- **Innovation-workforce ratio:** fraction of staff directly engaged in innovation projects, signalling social capability to drive circular transitions (García-Muiña et al., 2021)
- **Corporate-reputation index:** score based on the company’s presence and engagement on social networks, reflecting stakeholder trust in its digital circular initiatives (García-Muiña et al., 2021)
- **Job-creation indicator:** metric often used in circular-economy studies to capture employment generated by circular practices across industrial networks (Walker et al., 2021)
- **Inclusive industrialisation:** the extent to which digital-circular initiatives support broad-based economic participation and decent work (Iqbal et al., 2023).
- **Employee overtime hours:** Overtime work hours spent by total workforce (Oliveira Neto et al., 2023)

- **Working-environment and morale improvement:** assesses how digitally enabled circular operations enhance shop-floor conditions and employee morale (Ghaithan et al., 2023)
- **Labour-relations improvement:** gauges improvements in relations between management and staff stemming from data-driven circular initiatives — (Ghaithan et al., 2023)
- **Workers with higher education:** proportion of staff holding tertiary qualifications, signalling up-skilling demands of digital factories (Ali et al., 2022)

4.2. Bottom-up approach result – ARC

4.2.1. KPI creation for ARC

The outcomes from the bottom-up co-creation workshop conducted with ARC are presented as a set of measurable KPIs, designed to accurately track and evaluate the performance of technological developments relative to its defined business objectives. These results are detailed in Table 2.

Table 2: Creation of KPIs for ARC through bottom-up approach

Business Objective	KPI No.	KPI Name
Decrease cool test time	1	New cooling test time
	2	No. of FTE personnel for cooling test
	3	No. of returned products
	4	No. of daily refurbished products
	5	Refurbishment ratio
	6	Recycling rate
	7	Per-unit refurbishment cost – workforce
	8	Refurbishment productivity
	9	Rejection rate of new Automatic Sorting System
	10	No. of PCB's recovered /year

Decrease visual inspection time	11	Workstations for PCB recovery
	12	Cost savings in warranty claims & spare parts for PCBs
	13	No. of PCBs that are recovered
	14	FTE before automation
	15	Kg of lead and heavy metal recovered
Odour test	N.A	Due to technical limitation in the detection of bacterial colony size and bacterial growth detection using image processing, this BO “Odour test” is considered not applicable.
Reduce time and effort of testing	16	Total no. of stations for testing
	17	Total no. of processes for testing
	18	Total testing time for refurbished washing machine
	19	No. of automated/digital testing stations
Decrease the number of unnecessarily recycled refrigerators	20	Workstations in refurbishment workshop
	21	Products undergoing any value recovery
	22	Returned products in good condition
	23	Products eligible for recovery sent to recycling
	24	Refurbishment facility max capacity / year
	25	Utilization of refurbishment facility
Decrease sorting time	26	Average sorting time per unit
	27	Operator time savings
	28	Percentage reduction in sorting time
	Same as 5	Refurbishment ratio
	29	Scrap ratio

Increase utilization of refurbished parts	30	Spare part recovery ratio
	31	Revenue from refurbished parts (quarterly)
	32	Repairs/claims solved via spare-part recovery or refurbished machines
	33	Cost savings using refurbished parts vs. new

Note:

Odour test is marked as deviation as this DiCiM feature is not possible to develop within the course of the project. Hence KPI's related to this BO are not developed.

4.2.2. Description and Definition of KPI for ARC

For a comprehensive overview of the tailored and measurable KPIs identified for ARC, Table 3 provides detailed descriptions and definitions. Each KPI is clearly elaborated, ensuring alignment with ARC's strategic business objectives and technological development context.

Table 3: Description and definition of KPIs for ARC

KPI No.	KPI Name	Definition
1	New cooling test time	Average elapsed time to complete the cooling performance test on a new unit.
2	No. of FTE personnel for cooling test	Full-time equivalent staff dedicated to performing cooling tests.
3	No. of returned products	Total count of products returned by customers in a given period.
4	No. of daily refurbished products	Number of units fully refurbished and ready for resale each day.
5	Refurbishment ratio	Proportion of returned products successfully refurbished (refurbished ÷ returned).
6	Recycling rate	Percentage of returned items recycled or sent to WEEE ($\{\text{recycled} + \text{WEEE}\} \div \text{total returned}$).
7	Per-unit refurbishment cost – workforce	Average labour cost per refurbished unit (annual refurbished volume ÷ annual FTE wage).
8	Refurbishment productivity	Number of units refurbished per FTE per period (units ÷ FTE).
9	Rejection rate of new Automatic Sorting System	Share of items incorrectly rejected by the sorting system (rejected ÷ sorted).
10	No. of PCBs recovered / year	Total printed circuit boards salvaged for reuse or recycling annually.

11	Workstations for PCB recovery (manual)	Number of PCB recovery stations without automation or digital assistance.
12	Cost savings in warranty claims & spare parts for PCBs	Savings from using recovered PCBs versus new ones in warranty repairs.
13	No. of PCBs that are recovered	Total count of PCBs reclaimed for reuse or recycling.
14	FTE before automation (baseline)	Number of full-time staff pre-automation in the refurbishment facility.
15	Kg of lead and heavy metal recovered	Total weight of hazardous metals extracted and reclaimed.
16	Total no. of stations for testing	Count of all test stations in the facility.
17	Total no. of processes for testing	Number of distinct testing procedures applied to products.
18	Total testing time for refurbished washing machine	Cycle (takt) time required to fully test a refurbished washing machine.
19	Number of automated/digital testing stations	Count of test stations equipped with automation or digital tools.
20	Workstations in refurbishment workshop (manual)	Number of workshop stations not supported by automation or digital aids.
21	Products undergoing any value recovery	Total units processed for refurbishment, spare-part recovery, or other value-adding activities.
22	Returned products in good condition	Count of returns requiring no repair before resale or reuse.
23	Products eligible for recovery sent to recycling	Units suitable for recovery but directed to recycling instead.
24	Refurbishment facility max capacity / year	Maximum number of units the facility can refurbish in one year.
25	Utilization of refurbishment facility	Ratio of actual refurbished units to annual capacity.
26	Average sorting time per unit	Mean time to sort one unit (pre-automation baseline).
27	Operator time savings	Reduction in operator hours spent on sorting due to automation.
28	Percentage reduction in sorting time	Sorting-time decrease (%) compared to pre-automation baseline.
29	Scrap ratio	Share of returned products scrapped rather than refurbished or recycled.
30	Spare part recovery ratio	Proportion of salvaged spare parts relative to total available in returns.
31	Revenue from refurbished parts (quarterly)	Income earned from selling refurbished parts each quarter.
32	Repairs/claims solved via spare-part recovery or refurbished machines	Number of warranty repairs resolved using recovered parts or refurbished units.
33	Cost savings using refurbished parts vs. new	Savings achieved by using a refurbished part instead of a new one.

4.2.3. Identifying Potential Economic, Environmental and Social Implications of defined KPIs for ARC

Table 4 highlights the economic, environmental, and social implications of each KPI for ARC, thus providing an understanding of how monitoring and evaluating these KPIs will ultimately influence and enhance the demonstrator’s performance across the triple bottom line.

For instance, one of the KPIs identified for ARC specifically measures the duration of the new cooling test cycle. The implementation of machine learning algorithms as a technological feature is expected to accelerate these cooling cycle tests, thus generating significant economic implications through enhanced efficiency. Specifically, the reduction in test duration positively influences economics by leveraging the time value of money and lowering per-unit testing costs, directly impacted by operators’ hourly wages on the shop floor.

From an environmental perspective, this KPI is designed to reduce energy consumption, as shorter cooling cycles naturally decrease the amount of energy required to conduct refrigerator cooling tests. Consequently, this improvement aligns directly with sustainability goals by minimizing environmental impact.

Regarding social implications, this KPI addresses and mitigates the monotonous nature of manual testing tasks. By utilizing algorithmic decision-making, process reproducibility is enhanced, thereby increasing employee confidence in operational decisions. This improved decision-making capability reduces operator stress, boosts overall job satisfaction, and enhances workplace morale.

A similar evaluative methodology has been consistently applied across all KPIs, and comprehensive details of the economic, environmental, and social implications for each KPI are systematically presented in Table 4. This structured representation ensures clarity in assessing and justifying the impact of each KPI on the demonstrator’s triple bottom line.

Table 4: Analysis of economic, environmental and social impact of KPIs for ARC

BO No.	Business Objective	KPI No.	KPI	Economic Implication	Environmental Implication	Social Implication
1	Decrease cool test time	1	New cooling test time	Yes	Yes	Yes
		2	No. of FTE personnel for cooling test	Yes		
		3	No. of returned products	Yes	Yes	
		4	No. of daily refurbished products	Yes	Yes	
		5	Refurbishment ratio	Yes	Yes	
		6	Recycling rate	Yes	Yes	
		7	Per-unit refurbishment cost – workforce	Yes		
		8	Refurbishment productivity	Yes		Yes
		9	Rejection rate of new Automatic Sorting System	Yes	Yes	Yes
2	Decrease visual inspection time	10	No. of PCB's recovered /year	Yes	Yes	
		11	Workstations for PCB recovery	Yes		Yes
		12	Cost savings in warranty claims & spare parts for PCBs	Yes		
		13	No. of PCBs that are recovered	Yes	Yes	
		14	No. of FTE before automation			Yes
		15	Kg of lead and heavy metal recovered		Yes	Yes
3	Odour test	N.A.	–			
4	Reduce time and effort of testing	16	Total no. of stations for testing	Yes		Yes
		17	Total no. of processes for testing	Yes		Yes
		18	Total testing time for refurbished washing machine	Yes		Yes

		19	Number of automated/digital testing stations	Yes	Yes	
5	Decrease the number of unnecessarily recycled refrigerators	20	Workstations in refurbishment workshop	Yes	Yes	
		21	Products undergoing any value recovery	Yes	Yes	
		22	Returned products in good condition	Yes	Yes	
		23	Products eligible for recovery sent to recycling	Yes	Yes	
		24	Refurbishment facility max capacity / year	Yes		
		25	Utilization of refurbishment facility	Yes	Yes	
6	Decrease sorting time	26	Average sorting time per unit	Yes	Yes	
		27	Operator time savings	Yes	Yes	
		28	Percentage reduction in sorting time	Yes	Yes	
7	Increase utilization of refurbished parts	Same as 5	Refurbishment ratio	Yes	Yes	
		29	Scrap ratio	Yes	Yes	
		30	Spare part recovery ratio	Yes	Yes	
		31	Revenue from refurbished parts (quarterly)	Yes		
		32	Repairs/claims solved via spare-part recovery or refurbished machines	Yes	Yes	Yes
		33	Cost savings using refurbished parts vs. new	Yes		

4.3. Bottom-up approach result - GOR

4.3.1. KPI creation for GOR

The outcomes from the bottom-up co-creation workshop conducted with GOR are presented as a set of measurable KPIs, designed to accurately track and evaluate the performance of technological developments relative to its defined business objectives. These results are detailed in Table 5.

Table 5: Creation of KPIs for GOR through bottom-up approach

Business Objective	KPI No.	KPI
To optimize reverse logistics of used appliances/critical parts	1	Product volume return (measured annually/quarterly)
	2	Decision routing efficiency
	3	IoT connectivity rate
	4	WEEE routing rate
	5	Spare parts reuse rate
	6	Remanufacturing rate
	7	Inventory holding cost
	8	Secondary revenue
To speed up end-of prediction of remaining life of used parts/components	3	Same as KPI 3
	9	AI Prediction Volume
	10	Connected Device Prediction Coverage
	11	Average Predicted Lifetime in facility
Decrease testing time for new models of washing machines	12	No. of testing cycles for remanufactured parts or products
	13	Total time spent testing remanufactured parts or products
Increase uptime (lifetime) of washing machines	14	Average lifetime of products
	15	Repair success rate in use phase
	16	No. of repairs while in use phase
	17	Kg of material saved by using remanufactured/reused spare parts

	18	Cost reduced by using remanufactured/reused spare parts
	19	No. of repair successes via remanufactured/reused spare parts
Improve spare parts availability and inventory management	20	Inventory model updated with reclaimed spare parts
	21	New spare parts ordered from supplier
	22	Ratio of reclaimed spare part to new spare part inventory
Achieve low error rate in value recovery of returned appliances	23	Machine disassembly time (before and after AR-station assisted disassembly)
Lower time to provide product information	20	Same as KPI 20
	24	Access to product information for value recovery decisions
To enable sharing of product/component condition information with different partners	25	No. of internal departments with access to product lifecycle information
	26	No. of external partners with access to product lifecycle information
	27	No. of external partners with access to inventory data
	28	No. of internal departments with access to inventory data

4.3.2. Description and Definition of KPIs for GOR

For a comprehensive overview of the tailored and measurable KPIs identified for GOR, Table 6 provides detailed descriptions and definitions. Each KPI is clearly elaborated, ensuring alignment with GOR’s business objectives and technological development context.

Table 6: Description and definition of KPIs for GOR

KPI No.	KPI Name	Definition
1	Product volume return (measured annually/quarterly)	Total number of products returned over a year or quarter.
2	Decision routing efficiency	% of returned products correctly directed to remanufacturing, reuse, or recycling using data-driven decisions.
3	IoT connectivity rate	% of products monitored via IoT for tracking and data collection.
4	WEEE routing rate	% of returned products sent directly to WEEE processing.
5	Spare parts reuse rate	Number of salvaged spare parts that are reused versus the total parts recovered.
6	Remanufacturing rate	% of returned machines that are remanufactured or refurbished.
7	Inventory holding cost	Cost savings from minimizing non-sellable or damaged inventory.
8	Secondary revenue	Revenue generated from selling recovered parts, refurbished, or remanufactured products.
9	AI Prediction Volume	Total number of AI-driven predictions made per year.
10	Connected Device Prediction Coverage	% of IoT-connected products that receive data-driven decision-making predictions.
11	Average Predicted Lifetime in facility	Mean forecasted remaining useful life of products held in inventory.
12	No. of testing cycles for remanufactured parts or products	Total count of test iterations performed on remanufactured items.
13	Total time spent testing remanufactured parts or products	Cumulative hours spent in testing all remanufactured items.
14	Average lifetime of products	Mean operational lifespan of products before end-of-life return.
15	Repair success rate in use phase	% of in-field repairs that restore products to full functionality.
16	No. of repairs while in use phase	Count of repair events performed on products during their use phase.
17	Kg of material saved by using remanufactured/reused spare parts	Total weight of raw material conserved by repurposing parts instead of manufacturing new ones.
18	Cost reduced by using remanufactured/reused spare parts	Monetary savings achieved by using recovered parts versus purchasing new.
19	No. of repair successes via remanufactured/reused spare parts	Count of successful repairs using salvaged parts instead of new components.
20	Inventory model updated with reclaimed spare parts	Ability to update inventory model with reclaimed spare parts

21	New spare parts ordered from supplier	Total count of new spare parts that are ordered and are inbound from overseas.
22	Ratio of reclaimed spare part inventory to new part inventory	Proportion of reclaimed (remanufactured/reused) spare parts versus newly purchased parts.
23	Machine disassembly time (before and after AR-station assisted disassembly)	Comparison of elapsed time to disassemble units with and without AR-station assistance.
24	Access to product information for value recovery decisions	Yes/No indicator of whether lifecycle data is available to guide repair, remanufacturing, or disassembly.
25	No. of internal departments with access to product lifecycle information	Count of in-house teams granted visibility into product lifecycle data.
26	No. of external partners with access to product lifecycle information	Number of third-party organizations with permission to view lifecycle data.
27	No. of external partners with access to inventory data	Count of outside stakeholders able to see current inventory levels.
28	No. of internal departments with access to inventory data	Number of internal teams that can view real-time inventory information.

4.3.3. Identifying Potential Economic, Environmental and Social Implications of defined KPIs for GOR

Table 7 presents the economic, environmental, and social implications associated with each KPI identified for GOR, providing a clear and structured overview of how monitoring these KPIs directly impacts the demonstrator’s triple bottom line.

For instance, one of the KPIs for GOR tracks the secondary revenue generated from the sale of recovered parts, refurbished, or remanufactured products. This revenue stream emerges primarily from reusing critical components extracted from returned washing machines, which can then serve as spare parts for warranty claims, product lifecycle extension, and other repair purposes. Additional revenue streams include sales from refurbished washing machines and spare parts, as well as secondary service models such as pay-per-use or OEM spare parts replacement models. Collectively, these streams contribute to secondary revenue, directly linking this KPI to economic implications.

While extending product lifecycles, retaining value in spare parts, and maximizing utilization of products and components inherently have environmental benefits, these indirect environmental impacts are specifically tracked by another dedicated KPI - ‘Kg of material saved through

remanufactured/reused spare parts.’ Hence, the KPI discussed here focuses exclusively on its direct economic impact. Additionally, this KPI does not have an identified direct social implication.

A consistent evaluative methodology was systematically applied across all KPIs, and the comprehensive economic, environmental, and social impacts for each KPI are detailed clearly in Table 7. This structured methodology ensures transparency and thoroughness in assessing each KPI’s contribution to GOR’s triple bottom line.

Table 7: Analysis of economic, environmental and social impact of KPIs for GOR

BO No.	Business Objective	KPI No.	KPI	Economic Implications	Environmental implications	Social Implications
1	To optimize reverse logistics of used appliances/critical parts	1	Product volume return (measured annually/quarterly)	Yes	Yes	Yes
		2	Decision routing efficiency	Yes	Yes	
		3	IoT connectivity rate	Yes		
		4	WEEE routing rate	Yes	Yes	
		5	Spare parts reuse rate	Yes	Yes	
		6	Remanufacturing rate	Yes	Yes	
		7	Inventory holding cost	Yes		
		8	Secondary revenue	Yes		
2	To speed up end-of prediction of remaining life of used parts/components	3	Same as KPI 3	Yes		
		9	AI Prediction Volume	Yes	Yes	
		10	Connected Device Prediction Coverage	Yes		
		11	Average Predicted Lifetime in facility	Yes	Yes	
3	Decrease testing time for new models of washing machines	12	No. of testing cycles for remanufactured parts or products	Yes	Yes	
		13	Total time spent testing remanufactured parts or products	Yes	Yes	

4	Increase uptime (lifetime) of washing machines	14	Average lifetime of products	Yes	Yes	Yes
		15	Repair success rate in use phase	Yes	Yes	Yes
		16	No. of repairs while in use phase	Yes	Yes	Yes
		17	Kg of material saved by using remanufactured/reused spare parts	Yes	Yes	
		18	Cost reduced by using remanufactured/reused spare parts	Yes		
		19	No. of repair successes via remanufactured/reused spare parts	Yes		
5	Improve spare parts availability and inventory management	20	Inventory model updated with reclaimed spare parts	Yes		Yes
		21	New spare parts ordered from supplier	Yes	Yes	
		22	Ratio of reclaimed spare part to new spare part inventory	Yes	Yes	
6	Achieve low error rate in value recovery of returned appliances	23	Machine disassembly time (before and after AR-station assisted disassembly)	Yes		Yes
7	Lower time to provide product information	20	Same as KPI 20	Yes		
		24	Access to product information for value recovery decisions	Yes	Yes	Yes
8	To enable sharing of product/component condition information with different partners	25	No. of internal departments with access to product lifecycle information	Yes	Yes	Yes
		26	No. of external partners with access to product lifecycle information	Yes	Yes	Yes
		27	No. of external partners with access to inventory data	Yes	Yes	Yes
		28	No. of internal departments with access to inventory data	Yes	Yes	Yes

4.4. Bottom-up approach result - LEX

4.4.1. KPI creation for LEX

The outcomes from the bottom-up co-creation workshop conducted with LEX are presented as a set of measurable KPIs, designed to accurately track and evaluate the performance of technological developments relative to its defined business objectives. These results are detailed in Table 8.

Table 8: Creation of KPIs for LEX through bottom-up approach

Business Objective	KPI No.	KPI
Collect and Analyse Printer Usage Data	1	% of total devices capable of storing health check data
	2	% of devices capable of collecting IoT data
	3	% of printers flagging any error messages based on health-check data
	4	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data collection
	5	% of Non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data collection
	6	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data transfer
	7	% of Non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data transfer
	8	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data utilization for RL
	9	% of Non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data utilization for RL
	10	Existence of technology to facilitate data transfer for Non-MPS printers
	11	Kg CO ₂ -eq. per printed paper
	12	No. of parameters available for health-check data collection
Optimization of Reverse Logistics Based on Printer Usage Data	13	% of printers capable of IoT data considered for AI/ML-based reverse-logistics decision making
	14	% of reverse-logistics decisions made by AI engine that did not require manual testing
	15	% of printers directed towards WEEE recycler directly based on AI/ML engine
	16	% of eligible and usable printers coming back to the reverse-logistics centre (RLC)

Increase Number of Returned Non-MPS Printers	17	No. of printers returned – non-MPS (annual take-back volume)
	18	% of taken-back printers that undergo value recovery other than recycling (per year)
	19	Value recovery ratio (working efficiency)
Increase RLC Utilization Capacities	20	Average time spent on remanufacturing
	21	Average remanufacturing operations cost (at RLC)
	22	Average reverse-logistics cost for products inbounds to RLC
	23	Logistics cost from RLC to WEEE (outbound)
Increase Usage of Secondary Spare Parts and Optimize New Printer Production Spare Parts	24	% of components cannibalized
	25	No. of components undergoing remanufacture/repair/reuse
	26	% of printers cannibalized
	27	% utilization of end-of-life components upgraded to become spare parts
Increase Cartridge Returns for Non-MPS Printers	28	No. of restored lifecycles
	29	Kg CO ₂ -eq. reduction in emissions
	30	Cartridge value recovery ratio
	31	No. of cartridges returned

4.4.2. Description and Definition of KPIs for LEX

For a comprehensive overview of the tailored and measurable KPIs identified for LEX, Table 9 provides detailed descriptions and definitions. Each KPI is clearly elaborated, ensuring alignment with LEX's business objectives and technological development context.

Table 9: Description and definition of KPIs for LEX

KPI No.	KPI Name	Definition
1	% of total devices capable of storing health check data	Portion of all devices with onboard memory to record self-diagnostic health metrics.
2	% of devices capable of collecting IoT data	Share of devices equipped to gather and transmit IoT sensor measurements.
3	% of printers flagging any error messages based on health-check data	Proportion of printers that automatically generate error alerts from their health-check logs.
4	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data collection	Share of managed print service (MPS) devices able to record health metrics.
5	% of non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data collection	Share of non-MPS devices able to record self-diagnostic data.
6	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data transfer	Portion of MPS devices able to transmit collected health data to a central system.
7	% of non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data transfer	Portion of non-MPS devices able to send their health metrics to a backend.
8	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data utilization for RL	Share of MPS devices whose health data feeds into reverse-logistics decision tools.
9	% of non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data utilization for RL	Share of non-MPS devices whose health logs are used in reverse-logistics workflows.
10	Existence of technology to facilitate data transfer for non-MPS printers	Yes/No indicator of whether a solution exists to extract and send health data from non-MPS devices.
11	Kg CO ₂ -eq. per printed paper	Estimated greenhouse-gas emissions (in CO ₂ -equivalents) generated per printed sheet.
12	No. of parameters available for health-check data collection	Count of distinct sensor metrics (e.g., temperature, usage counters) recorded by devices.
13	% of printers capable of IoT data considered for AI/ML-based reverse-logistics decision making	Portion of IoT-enabled printers whose data feed is used by AI/ML models for reuse/remanufacture/recycle routing.
14	% of reverse-logistics decisions made by AI engine that did not require manual testing	Share of AI-driven routing outcomes validated without additional physical testing.
15	% of printers directed towards WEEE recycler directly based on AI/ML engine	Proportion of units automatically sent for WEEE processing by the AI/ML system.
16	% of eligible and usable printers coming back to the reverse-logistics centre (RLC)	Share of returned devices deemed fit for dismantling or remanufacturing that arrive at the RLC.
17	No. of printers returned – non-MPS (annual take-back volume)	Total count of non-MPS units collected through take-back programs each year.

18	% of taken-back printers that undergo value recovery other than recycling (per year)	Proportion of returned devices routed to reuse or remanufacture rather than direct recycling.
19	Value recovery ratio (working efficiency)	Fraction of returned units successfully converted into working products (reuse/remanufacture) versus total returns.
20	Average time spent on remanufacturing	Mean elapsed hours required to remanufacture a returned device.
21	Average remanufacturing operations cost (at RLC)	Mean cost per unit covering sorting, testing, cleaning, and packaging at the reverse-logistics centre.
22	Average reverse-logistics cost for products inbounds to RLC	Mean logistics expense to transport returned items into the facility.
23	Logistics cost from RLC to WEEE (outbound)	Average cost to send end-of-life units from the RLC to WEEE processors.
24	% of components cannibalized	Share of devices from which parts are discarded.
25	No. of components undergoing remanufacture/repair/reuse	Total count of salvaged parts processed for reuse, repair, or remanufacture.
26	% of printers cannibalized	Proportion of returned devices dismantled to supply parts for others.
27	% utilization of end-of-life components upgraded to become spare parts	Share of EoL parts successfully refurbished into inventory-grade spares.
28	No. of restored lifecycles	Count of units that completed at least one full reuse/remanufacture cycle.
29	Kg CO ₂ -eq. reduction in emissions (baseline = 1 lifecycle)	Total GHG savings (in CO ₂ -equivalents) achieved by reusing a product instead of new production.
30	Cartridge value recovery ratio	Proportion of ink/toner cartridges whose materials or components are reclaimed successfully.
31	No. of cartridges returned	Total count of empty or used cartridges collected for recovery or recycling.

4.4.3. Identifying Potential Economic, Environmental and Social Implications of defined KPIs for GOR

Table 10 summarizes the economic, environmental, and social implications associated with each KPI identified for LEX, clearly outlining how monitoring these KPIs contributes directly to the demonstrator's triple bottom line.

For example, one of the KPIs for LEX is "Existence of technology to facilitate data transfer for Non-MPS printers." Unlike conventional quantitative KPIs that typically address the question "By how much?",

this KPI uses a Boolean (Yes/No) approach based on the established baseline. Specifically, the KPI evaluates whether a technological method has been developed to transfer IoT sensor data from non-MPS printer segments. The goal within the DiCiM project is to enable the transfer of IoT data to support data-driven decision-making, particularly in reverse logistics processes for non-MPS printers. At the time of conducting the workshops and preparing this deliverable, the required technology was still under development, making this KPI particularly relevant as a milestone check.

Given that this KPI directly facilitates improved decision-making capabilities in reverse logistics, it primarily carries economic implications through enhanced operational efficiency and informed strategic decisions. While there may be indirect or transitive environmental benefits through optimized logistics and resource management, these are not directly captured by this specific KPI. Similarly, there is no direct social implication identified for this KPI, thus emphasizing its direct economic relevance.

A consistent evaluative methodology was systematically applied across all KPIs, and detailed economic, environmental, and social implications for each KPI are clearly summarized in Table 10. This structured approach ensures transparency, clarity, and comprehensive assessment of each KPI’s impact on LEX’s triple bottom line.

Table 10: Analysis of economic, environmental and social impact of KPIs for LEX

BO No.	Business Objective	KPI No.	KPI	Economic Implications	Environmental Implications	Social Implications
1	Collect and Analyse Printer Usage Data	1	% of total devices capable of storing health check data	Yes		
		2	% of devices capable of collecting IoT data	Yes		
		3	% of printers flagging any error messages based on health-check data	Yes		
		4	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data collection	Yes		

		5	% of Non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data collection	Yes		
		6	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data transfer	Yes		
		7	% of Non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data transfer	Yes		
		8	% of MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data utilization for RL	Yes		
		9	% of Non-MPS printers that can facilitate health-check data utilization for RL	Yes		
		10	Existence of technology to facilitate data transfer for Non-MPS printers	Yes		
		11	Kg CO ₂ -eq. per printed paper	Yes	Yes	
		12	No. of parameters available for health-check data collection	Yes		
2	Optimization of Reverse Logistics Based on Printer Usage Data	13	% of printers capable of IoT data considered for AI/ML-based reverse-logistics decision making	Yes	Yes	
		14	% of reverse-logistics decisions made by AI engine that did not require manual testing	Yes	Yes	Yes
		15	% of printers directed towards WEEE recycler directly based on AI/ML engine	Yes	Yes	Yes
		16	% of eligible and usable printers coming back to the reverse-logistics centre (RLC)	Yes	Yes	
3	Increase Number of Returned Non-MPS Printers	17	No. of printers returned – Non-MPS (annual take-back volume)	Yes	Yes	Yes
		18	% of taken-back printers that undergo value recovery other than recycling (per year)	Yes		
		19	Value recovery ratio (working efficiency)	Yes	Yes	
4		20	Average time spent on remanufacturing	Yes		

	Increase RLC Utilization Capacities	21	Average remanufacturing operations cost (at RLC)	Yes	
		22	Average reverse-logistics cost for products inbounds to RLC	Yes	
		23	Logistics cost from RLC to WEEE (outbound)	Yes	
5	Increase Usage of Secondary Spare Parts and Optimize New Printer Production Spare Parts	24	% of components cannibalized	Yes	Yes
		25	No. of components undergoing remanufacture/repair/reuse	Yes	Yes
		26	% of printers cannibalized	Yes	Yes
		27	% utilization of end-of-life components upgraded to become spare parts	Yes	Yes
6	Increase Cartridge Returns for Non-MPS Printers	28	No. of restored lifecycles	Yes	Yes
		29	Kg CO ₂ -eq. reduction in emissions		Yes
		30	Cartridge value recovery ratio	Yes	Yes
		31	No. of cartridges returned	Yes	Yes

4.5. Bottom-up approach result – C-ECO

4.5.1. KPI creation for C-ECO

The outcomes from the bottom-up co-creation workshop conducted with C-ECO are presented as a set of measurable KPIs, designed to accurately track and evaluate the performance of technological developments relative to its defined business objectives. These results are detailed in Table 11.

Table 11: Creation of KPIs for C-ECO through bottom-up approach

BO No.	Business Objective	KPI Number	KPI Name
1	Improve Data Integration	1	No. of Reports created in new dashboard
		2	No. of Systems/Data-sources connected to dashboards
		3	No. of reports accessible in a dashboard
		4	No. of logins at different systems to retrieve information for reporting/decision making
2*	Improve Data Transparency for Customer	1 to 4	Same as BO1 KPIs 1-4
		5	Average user's Feedback Rating
4	Increase predictability of the remanufacturers' supply-demand planning	6	Ability to provide forecast measure to facilitate demand planning
		7	Customer satisfaction indicating ease of planning downstream operations
5	Increase core returns		<i>This is an implicit connection, not directly influenced by DiCiM development - rather an outcome of DiCiM development. For this reason, KPI cannot be measured as this is a dynamic measurable.</i>
6	Reduce Sorting Errors	8	No. of flagged sorting-based errors (by AR glasses)
		9	% of accuracy of shipment
		10	% of order mismatch due to sorting error
7	Enable Proactive Error Prevention	11	No. of errors flagged by AR glasses and validated - Possibility to intervene proactively based on AR tech.
8	Reduce Effort for Training Operators	12	AR Glasses Functionality Score by Operators
		13	Operator Satisfaction in Using AR glasses
		14	Availability of Standardized Training Material
9	Reduce Time Needed to Prepare Reports	1	Same as KPI 1
		2	Same as KPI-2
		15	Ability to connect multiple data sources for report creation
		16	Average report turnaround time
		17	Manual creation of reports intervention frequency

		18	No. of standard reports
10	Reduce the number of support cases	19	No. of total tickets (Support / Service)
		20	No. of tickets avoidable through standardized reporting
		21	No. of escalated tickets
		22	No. of Service Desk, First & Second level support tickets older than 10 days – ONLY DiCiM related/ developments
11	Enable reporting scalability	1	Same as KPI 1
		20	Same as KPI 20
		3	Same as KPI 3
		23	% of customers or users actively accessing the portal (Adoption Rate)
		24	No. of views/downloads per report
12	Attract customers outside the automotive sector	25	Synergy sessions and mock pitches conducted
		26	Stakeholder engagement feedback
		27	Documentation of enablers and barriers
		28	Recommendations or follow-up actions generated from these engagements

Notes:

2 represents the combined BO's, BO2 and BO3 as for the demonstrator C-ECO, remanufacturers are its customers. Hence BO3 is a duplicate o BO2 so it is replaced with 2*.*

In the case of BO5 is a qualitative measure. Efforts cannot be calculated by frequency and time as this is a variable process itself. Efforts taken to quantify is not affecting working efficiency.

4.5.2. Description and Definition of KPIs for C-ECO

For a comprehensive overview of the tailored and measurable KPIs identified for C-ECO, Table 12 provides detailed descriptions and definitions. Each KPI is clearly elaborated, ensuring alignment with C-ECO's strategic business objectives and technological development context.

Table 12: Description and definition of KPIs for C-ECO

KPI No.	KPI Name	Definition
1	No. of reports created in new dashboard	Total count of distinct reports authored and saved within the new dashboard.
2	No. of systems/data-sources connected to dashboards	No. of unique data feeds integrated into the dashboard.
3	No. of reports accessible in a dashboard	No. of published reports end users can view or interact with.
4	No. of logins at different systems to retrieve information for reporting/decision making	Sum of user authentications across all source systems when gathering data.
5	Average user's feedback rating	Mean score (e.g., 1–5) given by users on dashboard usability and relevance.
6	Ability to provide forecast measure to facilitate demand planning	Yes/No indicator of whether predictive demand-planning metrics are available.
7	Customer satisfaction indicating ease of planning downstream operations	Average 5-point Likert score on how easily customers can plan operations based on insights.
8	No. of sorting-based errors flagged (by AR glasses)	Count of instances where AR-assisted sorting flagged potential mistakes.
9	% accuracy of shipment	Percentage of shipments correctly fulfilled ($\text{correct} \div \text{total} \times 100$).
10	No. of order mismatch due to sorting error	Proportion of orders with sorting-related errors ($\text{mismatches} \div \text{total} \times 100$).
11	No. of flagged errors by AR Glasses and validated	Number of AR-flagged errors confirmed as true upon review.
12	AR Glasses Functionality Score by Operators	Measures the usability and functional performance of AR glasses as experienced by warehouse operators. This includes clarity of instructions, responsiveness, reliability, and overall support for efficient sorting.
13	Operator Satisfaction in Using AR Glasses	Gauges how satisfied workers are with the experience of using AR glasses for sorting tasks, including ease of use, ease of adoption, and perceived impact on work performance.
14	Availability of Standardized Training Material	Assesses whether the organization provides structured and consistent training materials and procedures to help workers adopt and operate AR glasses effectively.
15	Ability to connect multiple data sources for report creation	Yes/No indicator of multi-source integration in one report.
16	Average report turnaround time	Mean elapsed time from ticket submission to report delivery.
17	Manual creation of reports intervention frequency	No. of manual interventions required in report generation workflows.

18	No. of standard reports (baseline)	Count of pre-defined templated reports (initially zero).
19	No. of total tickets (Support / Service)	Total support or service requests logged over a period.
20	No. of tickets avoidable through standardized reporting	Support tickets judged preventable by providing automated or standard reports.
21	No. of escalated tickets	Number of support tickets elevated to higher-level teams.
22	No. of tickets (SDCT, FLS, SLS) older than 10 days – ONLY DiCiM developments	Count of DiCiM-related tickets unaddressed for more than ten days.
23	% of customers or users actively accessing the portal (Adoption Rate)	Share of registered users who log into the portal at least once in a period (active ÷ total × 100).
24	No. of views/downloads per report	Average number of times each report is viewed or downloaded.
25	Synergy sessions and mock pitches conducted	Total count of collaborative workshops or practice presentations held.
26	Stakeholder engagement feedback	Summary score or qualitative rating from stakeholder sessions.
27	Documentation of enablers and barriers	Number of recorded findings on factors facilitating or hindering progress.
28	Recommendations or follow-up actions generated from these engagements	Count of actionable suggestions produced from stakeholder discussions.

4.5.3. Identifying Potential Economic, Environmental and Social Implications of defined KPIs for C-ECO

Table 13 outlines the economic, environmental, and social implications associated with each KPI for C-ECO, providing a structured overview of how measuring and monitoring these KPIs contribute directly to the demonstrator’s triple bottom line.

For example, one of the KPIs identified for C-ECO tracks the number of data sources and systems connected to the operational dashboard. An increased integration of various systems and data sources allows employees quicker access to relevant information, significantly reducing the time spent waiting for responses from cross-functional teams or searching for data. Economically, this leads to faster response times to customer inquiries, enhancing customer satisfaction and supporting C-ECO’s brand reputation. Additionally, it enables employees to manage their tasks more efficiently, directly improving operational effectiveness.

In terms of environmental impact, this specific KPI does not present direct implications. Socially, however, the integration significantly enhances employee productivity and workflow efficiency, as individuals gain immediate access to essential information required to fulfil their roles. This empowers employees, promotes greater self-sufficiency, and contributes positively to overall job satisfaction and streamlined workflows. Consequently, this KPI primarily carries economic and social implications.

A consistent evaluative methodology was applied to all KPIs, and the detailed economic, environmental, and social impacts for each KPI are systematically summarized in Table 13. This structured approach ensures a clear and thorough assessment of each KPI’s influence on C-ECO’s triple bottom line.

Table 13: Analysis of economic, environmental and social impact of KPIs for C-ECO

BO No.	Business Objective	KPI Number	KPI Name	Economic Implications	Environmental Implications	Social Implications
1	Improve Data Integration	1	No. Of Reports created in new dashboard	Yes		Yes
		2	No. Of Systems/Data-sources connected to dashboards	Yes		Yes
		3	No. of reports accessible in a dashboard	Yes		Yes
		4	No. of logins at different systems to retrieve information for reporting/decision making	Yes		Yes
2*	Improve Data Transparency for Customer	1 to 4	Same as BO1 KPI’s 1-4	Yes		Yes
		5	Average user's Feedback Rating (user = reman, wholesaler, operations, etc.)	Yes		
4	Increase predictability of the remanufacturers' supply-demand planning	6	Ability to provide forecast measure to facilitate demand planning (yes/no)	Yes	Yes	
		7	Customer satisfaction indicating ease of planning downstream operations (5-point Likert scale)	Yes		
5	Increase core returns		This is an implicit connection, not directly influenced by DiCiM			

			development - rather an outcome of DiCiM development. For this reason, KPI cannot be measured as this is a dynamic measurable.			
6	Reduce Sorting Errors	8	No. of sorting-based errors flagged (by AR glasses)	Yes	Yes	Yes
		9	% of accuracy of shipment (derived from Excel sheet)	Yes	Yes	
		10	% of order mismatch due to sorting error (derived from Excel sheet)	Yes	Yes	
7	Enable Proactive Error Prevention	11	No. of flagged errors by AR glasses and validated - Possibility to intervene proactively based on AR tech.	Yes		
8	Reduce Effort for Training Operators	12	AR Glasses Functionality Score by Operators	Yes		Yes
		13	Operator Satisfaction in Using AR Goggles	Yes		Yes
		14	Availability of Standardized Training Material	Yes		Yes
9	Reduce Time Needed to Prepare Reports	1	Same as KPI 1 in BO1	Yes		Yes
		2	same as KPI-2	Yes		Yes
		15	Ability to connect multiple data sources for report creation (Yes/No)	Yes		Yes
		16	Average report turnaround time: elapsed time from ticket initiation to report delivery	Yes		
		17	Manual creation of reports intervention frequency (Number of manual interventions of C-ECO personal)	Yes		
		18	No. of standard reports (baseline, we set this to zero)	Yes		
10	Reduce the number of support cases	19	No. of total tickets (Support / Service)	Yes		
		20	No. of tickets that could have been avoided through standardized reporting (has challenges)	Yes		
		21	No. Of Escalated tickets	Yes		
		22	No. of tickets (SDCT, FLS, SLS - assigned to different organization levels) that are	Yes		

older than 10 days - ONLY DiCiM developments						
11	Enable reporting scalability	1	No. of reports created in the integrated dashboard --> →same as KPI1	Yes		Yes
		20	KPI-20 from BO-9	Yes		
		3	No. of Reports Made Accessible to Customers via Portal --> same as KPI3	Yes		Yes
		23	% of customers or users actively accessing the portal (Reporting Portal Adoption Rate)	Yes		
		24	No. of views/ downloads per report	Yes		
12	Attract customers outside the automotive sector	25	Synergy sessions and mock pitches conducted	Yes	Yes	Yes
		26	Stakeholder engagement feedback	Yes		
		27	Documentation of enablers and barriers	Yes		
		28	Recommendations or follow-up actions generated from these engagements	Yes	Yes	

5. Discussions

This chapter critically evaluates the outcomes of both the top-down and bottom-up methodological approaches utilized in KPI creation. It emphasizes the comparative effectiveness of these methods in generating KPIs relevant to demonstrators' specific business contexts and discusses insights obtained from direct stakeholder engagement regarding the practical interpretation and applicability of these KPIs.

5.1. Comparative Analysis of Top-down and Bottom-up Approaches

The top-down approach, primarily conducted through a systematic literature review, provided a broad but largely generic list of KPIs, frequently addressing system-level impacts within the context of circular economy initiatives. The literature predominantly comprises conceptual frameworks and reviews, with relatively fewer empirical investigations. However, it consistently identifies digitalization as a significant enabler of circular economy initiatives in manufacturing sectors, particularly through Circular Manufacturing Systems (CMS). Although these system-level KPIs offer valuable insights, they generally lack the specificity required to directly guide demonstrators' strategic decisions and investments in digitalization. Hence there was a clear miss for direct reproducibility of most KPI's for demonstrators.

In contrast, the bottom-up approach, involving direct co-creation workshops with demonstrators, resulted in the development of highly tailored KPIs closely aligned with the demonstrators' explicit business objectives and technological development goals. This specificity arose from comprehensive discussions about business needs, financial and non-financial motivations, operational efficiencies, and process optimization. The bottom-up approach effectively addressed the limitations of the generic KPIs identified through literature review by providing precise and actionable performance measures, reflecting the demonstrators' actual operational and strategic contexts.

Thus, the comparative analysis underscores the superior practicality and relevance of the bottom-up approach, as it integrates demonstrators' direct input and specific business logic, ensuring the development of KPIs that are actionable, relevant, and directly applicable within their operational frameworks.

5.2. Reflections on Demonstrators' Perceptions of KPIs

Through the bottom-up workshops, it became apparent that the concept of KPIs, particularly those related to the environmental and social verticals of the triple bottom line, was initially challenging for demonstrators. Traditionally, businesses predominantly focus on economic performance indicators, primarily driven by profitability, operational efficiency, process optimization, return on investment, time value of money and related economic parameters. Consequently, many demonstrators initially gravitated towards conventional KPIs, viewing them primarily through an economic lens.

However, during the workshops, a progressive understanding emerged among demonstrators regarding environmental and social KPIs. Although demonstrators demonstrated a clear commitment to positively influencing environmental and social aspects through their operations, translating this commitment into measurable KPIs initially posed difficulties due to a lack of familiarity and practical experience in tracking and interpreting such non-economic impacts.

The iterative and collaborative nature of the bottom-up workshops allowed demonstrators to deepen their understanding of how their business activities and technological advancements could systematically influence the triple bottom line. This process facilitated the identification and articulation of relevant environmental and social impacts of measurable list of KPIs, illustrating the broader impacts of digitalization and circular economy strategies. As the workshops progressed, demonstrators began to appreciate the interconnected nature of economic, environmental, and social objectives, resulting in a more balanced and holistic set of performance measures.

In summary, while traditional economic-focused KPIs remain critical for demonstrators, the workshops effectively expanded their perspective, enabling them to recognize and articulate the broader implications of their business activities on the triple bottom line. This increased awareness and capability to measure environmental and social impacts significantly enhances demonstrators' capacity to pursue sustainable business practices alongside economic growth.

6. Conclusion and Future Directions

This report aimed to systematically identify, define, and evaluate measurable Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) to assess the socio-economic and environmental impacts of digital technologies within circular economy contexts for the DiCiM project's demonstrators: Arcelik (ARC), Gorenje (GOR), Lexmark (LEX) and Circular Economy GmbH (C-ECO). Recognizing the complexity and specificity required in KPI development, the report adopted a dual methodological approach consisting of a top-down systematic literature review and a bottom-up co-creation process involving demonstrators.

The top-down literature review leveraged the Scopus database to explore existing scholarly discourse, identifying a broad range of KPIs associated primarily with the economic, environmental, and social impacts of digitalization and circular economy initiatives in manufacturing. Despite its comprehensive coverage, the literature predominantly offered generic, conceptual, and system-level KPIs with limited empirical evidence, highlighting gaps in practical applicability for specific business contexts.

To address this limitation, a complementary bottom-up approach was employed through iterative co-creation workshops with demonstrators. These workshops facilitated direct engagement, allowing each demonstrator to articulate business-specific objectives, operational contexts, and technological developments clearly. This collaborative approach resulted in tailored KPIs, ensuring direct relevance, usability, and alignment with demonstrators' strategic goals and operational realities.

Through comparative analysis, the bottom-up approach clearly demonstrated its superiority in generating precise, practical, and actionable KPIs compared to the broader, conceptual indicators from the literature review. However, insights from the literature provided valuable context, establishing the broader importance of balancing economic, environmental, and social considerations within circular economy frameworks.

The discussion chapter highlighted critical insights from the workshops, particularly the initial challenges demonstrators faced in understanding and integrating environmental and social KPIs. Despite traditionally focusing on economic measures, demonstrators progressively recognized the importance and feasibility of systematically measuring and managing broader triple bottom line impacts. The iterative workshop process significantly enhanced demonstrators' capability and

confidence in identifying meaningful KPIs that reflect comprehensive business performance beyond mere economic returns.

Overall, this report successfully delivered a robust methodological framework and specific, contextually relevant KPIs for each demonstrator. It provided clarity on the benefits of integrating tailored KPIs derived from direct stakeholder involvement, underscoring the necessity for a balanced approach to evaluating digital technologies' impacts across the triple bottom line.

This deliverable D6.1 lays essential groundwork for Work Package WP6, particularly serving as the cornerstone for deliverable D6.2, which focuses on the measurement of these identified KPIs. In task 6.2, demonstrators will proactively measure the feasible KPIs detailed in subchapters 4.2, 4.3, 4.4, and 4.5 for ARC, GOR, LEX and C-ECO respectively. Once demonstrators identify feasible KPIs from this measurable set, they will establish a baseline year and baseline conditions. This process will enable precise determination of each KPI's impact on the performance of demonstrators' business objectives, thus clearly identifying their contributions to the triple bottom line.

Furthermore, this deliverable sets the stage for subsequent tasks within WP6: task 6.3, which involves determining demonstrator-level scalability impacts, and task 6.4, which examines scalability potential and broader business impacts at the sector level.

7. References

- Abdul-Hamid, A.Q., Ali, M.H., Tseng, M.L., Ali, N. & Babuna, P. (2020) 'Impeding challenges on Industry 4.0 in circular economy: palm-oil industry in Malaysia', *Computers & Operations Research*, 123, 105052.
- Ahi, P. & Searcy, C. (2015) 'An analysis of metrics used to measure performance in green and sustainable supply chains', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 86, 360–377.
- Ajwani-Ramchandani, R., Figueira, S., Torres de Oliveira, R. & Jha, S. (2021) 'Enhancing the circular and modified linear economy: the importance of blockchain for developing economies', *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 168, 105468.
- Alam, S.S., Latif, M.M., Kokash, H.A. & Ahsan, M.N. (2025) 'Relationship among Industrial IoT, Circular Supply Chain Management Practices and Sustainable Performance of Manufacturing Companies: an Empirical Study', *Circular Economy and Sustainability*.
- Ali, Q., Parveen, S., Yaacob, H. & Zaini, Z. (2022) 'The management of Industry 4.0 technologies and environmental assets for optimal performance of industrial firms in Malaysia', *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 29, 52964–52983.
- Alves, L., Ferreira Cruz, E., Lopes, S.I. et al. (2022) 'Towards a circular economy in the textiles and clothing value chain through blockchain technology and IoT: a review', *Waste Management & Research*, 40(1), 3–23.
- Arioli, V., Ruggeri, G., Sala, R., Pirola, F. & Pezzotta, G. (2023) 'A methodology for the design and engineering of smart product service systems: an application in the manufacturing sector', *Sustainability*, 15(1), Article 64.
- Atif, S., Ahmed, S., Wasim, M. et al. (2021) 'Towards a conceptual development of Industry 4.0, servitisation, and circular economy: a systematic literature review', *Sustainability*, 13(11), 6501.
- Asif, A., M, F., 2017. *Circular Manufacturing Systems : A development framework with analysis methods and tools for implementation*.
- Awan, U., Sroufe, R. & Shahbaz, M. (2021) 'Industry 4.0 and the circular economy: a literature review and recommendations for future research', *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 30(4), 2038–2060.
- Bag, S., Wood, L.C., Mangla, S.K. & Luthra, S. (2020a) 'Procurement 4.0 and its implications on business-process performance in a circular economy', *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 152, 104502.
- Bag, S., Yadav, G., Wood, L.C. et al. (2020b) 'Industry 4.0 and the circular economy: resource melioration in logistics', *Resources Policy*, 68, 101776.
- Bag, S., Gupta, S., Kumar, S., 2021. Industry 4.0 adoption and 10R advance manufacturing capabilities for sustainable development. *International Journal of Production Economics* 231, 107844.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.107844>
- Bag, S., Yadav, G., Dhamija, P. & Kataria, K.K. (2021) 'Key resources for Industry 4.0 adoption and its effect on sustainable production and circular economy: an empirical study', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 281, 125233.

Bahadori, N., Kaymak, T. & Seraj, M. (2021) 'Environmental, social, and governance factors in emerging markets: the impact on firm performance', *Business Strategy & Development*, 4, 411–422.

Bressanelli, G., Adrodegari, F., Pigosso, D.C.A. & Parida, V. (2022) 'Towards the smart circular economy paradigm: a definition, conceptualization, and research agenda', *Sustainability*, 14(9), 4960.

Bressanelli, G., Sacconi, N. & Perona, M. (2024) 'Are digital servitization-based circular economy business models sustainable? A systemic what-if simulation model', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 458, 142512.

Centobelli, P., Cerchione, R., Del Vecchio, P., Oropallo, E. & Secundo, G. (2022) 'Blockchain technology for bridging trust, traceability and transparency in circular supply chain', *Information & Management*, 59, 103508.

Cavaliere, A., Reis, J. & Amorim, M. (2024) 'Socio-environmental assessment and application process for IoT: a comprehensive approach', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 436, 140348.

Cerreta, M., Mura, F., Della Lieto, L. & Poli, G. (2020) 'Short-term city dynamics: effects and proposals before the COVID-19 pandemic', *Aestimum*, 77, 147–169.

Chang, Y., Ming, X., Liao, X., Bao, Y., Chen, Z. & Song, W. (2023) 'Sustainable value creation through customization for smart PSS models: a multi-industry case study', *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 35(1), 29–53.

Chauhan, C., Parida, V., Dhir, A., 2022. Linking circular economy and digitalisation technologies: A systematic literature review of past achievements and future promises. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change* 177, 121508. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.techfore.2022.121508>

Chou, C.-J., Chen, C.-W. & Conley, C. (2015) 'An approach to assessing sustainable product-service systems', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 86, 277–284.

Condemi, A., Cucchiella, F. & Schettini, D. (2019) 'Circular economy and e-waste: an opportunity from RFID TAGs', *Applied Sciences*, 9(16), 3422.

de Filippi, F. & Carbone, C. (2021) 'ICT as innovative tools for circular planning in urban areas', *Techne*, 22(1), 96–103.

de Mattos Nascimento, D.L., Alencastro, V., Quelhas, O.L.G., Caiado, R.G.G., Garza-Reyes, J.A., Rocha-Lona, L. & Tortorella, G. (2018) 'Exploring Industry 4.0 technologies to enable circular economy practices in a manufacturing context: a business model proposal', *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 30, 607–627.

de Mattos Nascimento, D.L., Nepomuceno, R.M., Caiado, R.G.G. et al. (2022) 'A sustainable circular 3D-printing model for recycling metal scrap in the automotive industry', *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 33(5), 876–892.

de Souza, M., Pereira, G.M., Jabbour, A.B.L. et al. (2021) 'A digitally enabled circular economy for mitigating food waste: understanding innovative marketing strategies in an emerging economy', *Technological Forecasting & Social Change*, 173, 121062.

Del Giudice, M., Chierici, R., Mazzucchelli, A. & Fiano, F. (2020) ‘Supply-chain management in the era of circular economy: the moderating effect of big data’, *The International Journal of Logistics Management*, 32(2), 337–356.

Dev, N.K., Shankar, R. & Qaiser, F.H. (2020) ‘Industry 4.0 and circular economy: operational excellence for sustainable reverse supply chain performance’, *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 153, 104583.

Di Maria, E., De Marchi, V. & Galeazzo, A. (2022) ‘Industry 4.0 technologies and circular economy: the mediating role of supply-chain integration’, *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31(2), 619–632.

Dominish, E., Retamal, M., Sharpe, S. et al. (2018) ‘“Slowing” and “narrowing” the flow of metals for consumer goods: evaluating opportunities and barriers’, *Sustainability*, 10(4), 1096.

European Commission, 2019. Green transition - European Commission [WWW Document]. URL https://reform-support.ec.europa.eu/what-we-do/green-transition_en (accessed 6.24.25).

Faria, R., Lopes, I., Pires, I.M. et al. (2020) ‘Circular economy for clothes using web and mobile technologies – a systematic review and a taxonomy proposal’, *Information*, 11(3), 161.

Feil, A.A., de Quevedo, D.M. & Schreiber, D. (2015) ‘Selection and identification of indicators for quickly measuring sustainability in micro and small furniture industries’, *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 3, 34–44.

Felsberger, A. & Reiner, G. (2020) ‘Sustainable Industry 4.0 in production and operations management: a systematic literature review’, *Sustainability*, 12, 7982.

Fofou, R.F., Jiang, Z. & Wang, Y. (2021) ‘A review on the life-cycle strategies enhancing remanufacturing’, *Applied Sciences*, 11(13), 5937.

Fraga-Lamas, P., Lopes, S.I. & Fernández-Caramés, T.M. (2021) ‘Green IoT and edge AI as key technological enablers for a sustainable digital transition towards a smart circular economy’, *Sensors*, 21(17), 5745.

García-Muiña, F., Medina-Salgado, M.S., González-Sánchez, R. et al. (2021) ‘Industry 4.0-based dynamic Social Organizational Life Cycle Assessment to target the social circular economy in manufacturing’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 327, 129439.

Ghathian, A.M., Alshammakhi, Y., Mohammed, A. & Mazher, K.M. (2023) ‘Integrated impact of circular economy, Industry 4.0, and lean manufacturing on sustainability performance of manufacturing firms’, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 20(6), 5119.

Gupta, A., Vangari, R., Jayal, A.D. & Jawahir, I.S. (2011) ‘Priority evaluation of product metrics for sustainable manufacturing’, in Bernard, A. (ed.) *Global Product Development*. Berlin Heidelberg: Springer, 631–641.

Hester, P., Ezell, B., Collins, A., Horst, J., Lawsure, K., 2017. A Method for Key Performance Indicator Assessment in Manufacturing Organizations. *Int J Oper Res* 14, 157–167.

Hettiarachchi, B.D., Seuring, S. & Brandenburg, M. (2022) ‘Industry 4.0-driven operations and supply chains for the circular economy: a bibliometric analysis’, *Operations Management Research*, 15, 858–878.

- Hoosain, M.S., Paul, B.S. & Ramakrishna, S. (2020) ‘The impact of 4IR digital technologies and circular thinking on the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals’, *Sustainability*, 12(23), 10143.
- Iqbal, A. et al. (2023) ‘Waste as resource for Pakistan: an innovative business model of regenerative circular economy to integrate municipal solid-waste management sector’, *Sustainability*, 15(7), 6281.
- Imtanavanich, P. & Gupta, S.M. (2006) ‘Solving a disassembly-to-order system by using genetic algorithm and weighted fuzzy goal programming’, *Optics East 2006*, Boston, MA: SPIE, 638506.
- Kamble, S.S., Gunasekaran, A., Ghadge, A. & Raut, R. (2020) ‘A performance measurement system for Industry 4.0 enabled smart manufacturing system in SMMEs: a review and empirical investigation’, *International Journal of Production Economics*, 229, 107853.
- Khan, S.A.R., Piprani, A.Z. & Yu, Z. (2022a) ‘Digital technology and circular-economy practices: future of supply chains’, *Operations Management Research*, 15(2), 676–688.
- Khan, S.A.R., Umar, M., Asadov, A., Tanveer, M. & Yu, Z. (2022b) ‘Technological revolution and circular economy practices: a mechanism of green economy’, *Sustainability*, 14(8), 4524.
- Khan, A.Y., Akhtar, M. & Khan, A.Y. (2024) ‘Digitalization for a Sustainable Performance: dual-study analysis of digital leadership, circular economy, and technological innovation’, *Sustainability*, 16, 10465.
- Kristoffersen, E., Blomsma, F., Mikalef, P. & Li, J. (2020) ‘The smart circular economy: a digital-enabled circular strategies framework for manufacturing companies’, *Journal of Business Research*, 120, 241–261.
- Krstić, M., Agnusdei, G.P., Miglietta, P.P. & Chini, T. (2022) ‘Applicability of Industry 4.0 technologies in reverse logistics: a circular-economy approach based on the COBRA method’, *Sustainability*, 14(9), 5632.
- Luciano, A., Cutaia, L., Cioffi, F. & Sinibaldi, C. (2021) ‘Demolition and construction recycling unified management: the DECORUM platform for improvement of resource efficiency in the construction sector’, *Environmental Science & Pollution Research*, 28, 24558–24569.
- Magrini, C., Nicolas, J., Berg, H. et al. (2021) ‘Using Internet of Things and distributed ledger technology for digital circular economy enablement: the case of electronic equipment’, *Sustainability*, 13(9), 4982.
- Masi, D., Day, S. & Godsell, J. (2017) ‘Supply-chain configurations in the circular economy: a systematic literature review’, *Sustainability*, 9(9), 1602.
- Matarneh, S., Piprani, A.Z., Ellahi, R.M., Nguyen, D.N., Le, T.M. & Nazir, S. (2024) ‘Industry 4.0 technologies and circular economy synergies: enhancing corporate sustainability through sustainable supply-chain integration and flexibility’, *Environmental Technology & Innovation*, 35, 103723.
- Millard, J., Sorivelle, M.N., Deljanin, S., Unterfrauner, E. & Voigt, C. (2018) ‘Is the maker movement contributing to sustainability?’, *Sustainability*, 10(7), 2212.
- Moreno, M., Court, R., Wright, M. & Charnley, F. (2019) ‘Opportunities for redistributed manufacturing and digital intelligence as enablers of a circular economy’, *International Journal of Sustainable Engineering*, 12(2), 77–94.

Neri, A., Cagno, E., Susur, E., Urueña, A., Nuur, C., Kumar, V., Franchi, S., Sorrentino, C., 2025. The relationship between digital technologies and the circular economy: a systematic literature review and a research agenda. *R&D Management* 55, 617–713. <https://doi.org/10.1111/radm.12715>

Oliveira Neto, G.C. de, de Araujo, S.A., Gomes, R.A., Alliprandini, D.H., Flausino, F.R. & Amorim, M. (2023) 'Simulation of electronic-waste reverse chains for the São Paulo circular economy: an artificial intelligence-based approach for economic and environmental optimizations', *Sensors*, 23, 9046.

Rahdari, A.H. & Anvary Rostamy, A.A. (2015) 'Designing a general set of sustainability indicators at the corporate level', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 108, 757–771.

Rashid, A., Roci, M., Asif, F.M.A., 2020. Circular manufacturing systems, in: *Handbook of the Circular Economy*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 343–357. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781788972727.00036>

Rejeb, A., Suhaiza, Z., Rejeb, K. et al. (2022) 'The Internet of Things and the circular economy: a systematic literature review and research agenda', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 350, 131439.

Ren, S., Zhang, Y., Liu, Y., Sakao, T. & Huisingh, D. (2019) 'A comprehensive review of big data analytics throughout product lifecycle to support sustainable smart manufacturing', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 210, 1343–1365.

Rüßmanns, M., Lorenz, M., Gerbert, P., Waldner Manuela, Engel Pascal, Harnisch Michael, Justus Jan, 2015.

Industry 4.0: The Future of Productivity and Growth in Manufacturing Industries [WWW Document]. BCG Global. URL

https://www.bcg.com/publications/2015/engineered_products_project_business_industry_4_future_productivity_growth_manufacturing_industries (accessed 6.24.25).

Sahoo, S., Upadhyay, A., 2024. Improving triple bottom line (TBL) performance: analyzing impacts of industry 4.0, lean six sigma and circular supply chain management. *Ann Oper Res*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10479-024-05945-2>

Sassanelli, C. & Terzi, S. (2023) 'Circular economy and sustainable business performance management', *Sustainability*, 15, 8619.

Sangwa, N.R. & Sangwan, K.S. (2017) 'Development of an integrated performance measurement framework for lean organizations', *Journal of Manufacturing Technology Management*, 29, 41–84.

Shahbazi, S., Jönsson, C., Wiktorsson, M., Kurdve, M. & Bjelkemyr, M. (2018) 'Material efficiency measurements in manufacturing: Swedish case studies', *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 181, 17–32.

Tang, Y.M., Chau, K.Y., Fatima, A. & Waqas, M. (2022) 'Industry 4.0 technology and circular economy practices: business management strategies for environmental sustainability', *Environmental Science & Pollution Research*, 29(38), 49752–49769.

Townsend, J.H. & Coroama, V.C. (2018) 'Digital acceleration of sustainability transition: the paradox of push impacts', *Sustainability*, 10(8), 2816.

Vaccaro, G. & Buoninconti, L. (2021) '3D print e circular economy: innovation and sustainability for the construction sector', *Sustainable Mediterranean Construction*, 13(2), 73–82.

Vadde, S., Zeid, A. & Kamarthi, S.V. (2011) ‘Pricing decisions in a multi-criteria setting for product recovery facilities’, *Omega*, 39, 186–193.

Valenzuela-Venegas, G., Salgado, J.C. & Díaz-Alvarado, F.A. (2016) ‘Sustainability indicators for the assessment of eco-industrial parks: classification and criteria for selection’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 133, 99–116.

Waibel, M.W., Steenkamp, L.P., Moloko, N. & Oosthuizen, G.A. (2017) ‘Investigating the effects of smart production systems on sustainability elements’, *Procedia Manufacturing*, 8, 731–737.

Walker, A.M., Opferkuch, K., Lindgreen, E.R., Simboli, A., Vermeulen, W.J. & Raggi, A. (2021) ‘Assessing the social sustainability of circular-economy practices: industry perspectives from Italy and The Netherlands’, *Sustainable Production and Consumption*, 27, 831–844.

Wang, N., Ren, S., Liu, Y., Yang, M. & Wang, J. (2020) ‘An active preventive maintenance approach of complex equipment based on a novel product-service system operation mode’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 277, 123365.

Warmington-Lundström, J. & Laurenti, R. (2020) ‘Reviewing circular economy rebound effects: the case of online peer-to-peer boat sharing’, *Resources, Conservation & Recycling X*, 5, 100028.

Wasono, L.W. & Furinto, A. (2018) ‘The effect of digital leadership and innovation management for incumbent telecommunication company in the digital disruptive era’, *International Journal of Engineering & Technology*, 7, 125–130.

Watson, K.J., Evans, J., Karvonen, A. & Whitley, T. (2016) ‘Capturing the social value of buildings: the promise of Social Return on Investment (SROI)’, *Building and Environment*, 103, 289–301.

Yadav, G., Luthra, S., Jakhar, S.K., Mangla, S.K. & Rai, D.P. (2020) ‘A framework to overcome sustainable supply-chain challenges through solution measures of Industry 4.0 and circular economy: an automotive case’, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 254, 120112.

Yu, Z., Khan, S.A.R. & Umar, M. (2022) ‘Circular economy practices and Industry 4.0 technologies: a strategic move of automobile industry’, *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 31, 796–809.

8. Annex A – Workshop Design

Figure 3 represents the design of workshop to facilitate data collection through the bottom-up approach for KPI creation for LEX. This figure represents the questions raised to the demonstrators during the workshop in a semi-structured and open ended interview format for the workshops. Similar methodology for data collection was utilized for ARC, GOR and C-ECO.

Business Objective	Is this measurement still relevant for you? (Y/N)	How do you measure the impact of business objectives in:			Are you measuring this now? (Y/N)	What are you measuring?	How do you measure it – Are there any sub-metrics that enable the measurement of this KPI?	Do you have the data to measure this? (Y/N)	What is the data you need (N) or in use (Y)	Are there any challenges in measuring the KPI	Are there Other KPI's you are measuring?
		Environment	Social	Economic							
To optimize reverse logistics of used appliances/critical parts											
To speed up end-of-life testing of used parts/components											
Decrease testing time for new models of washing machines											
Increase uptime of washing machines											
Improve spare parts availability and inventory management											
Achieve low error rate in value recovery of returned appliances											
Lower time to provide product information											
To enable sharing of product/component condition information with different partners											

Figure 3: Design of bottom-up workshop for LEX

9. Annex B – Mapping BO to KPIs mentioned in DOA

Table 14 represents the mapping of Business Objectives of ARC to the measurements mentioned in the DOA.

Table 14: Mapping business objectives of ARC to measurements mentioned in DOA

Business Objective	Measurements mentioned in the DOA
Decrease cool test time	
Decrease visual inspection time	
Decrease costs and time for odour test	
Reduce time and effort for testing	
Decrease the number of unnecessary recycled refrigerators	Increase spare parts recovery rate: 150% from the current state
	Volume returns: 70,000 units (net material saving: 7,000 tonnes)
	Increase in spare part recovery rate: 150% (from the current state)
Decrease sorting time	
Increase utilization of refurbished parts for repairs	Potential net value savings: €13.6 million (average price: €130)

Table 15 represents the mapping of Business Objectives of GOR to the measurements mentioned in the DOA.

Table 15: Mapping business objectives of GOR to measurements mentioned in DOA

Business Objective	Measurements mentioned in DOA
To optimize reverse logistics of used appliances/critical parts	Increase in Spare Part Recovery Rate:
	Recovery rate improvement: 20%
	Net value savings: €4.2 million (based on average B-stock price of €210)
	Loss reduction: €190,000
	Net material savings: 2,920 tons (average 146 kg per WM-TD unit)
	Increase in Logistics Efficiency:
	Improvement target: 50%
	Size of B-stock Washing Machines (WM) & Tumble Dryers (TD):
Annual target: 20,000 units per year	
To speed up end-of-life testing of used parts/components	
Decrease testing time for new models of washing machines	
Increase uptime of washing machines	
Improve spare parts availability and inventory management	Increase in Spare Part Recovery Rate:
	Recovery rate improvement: 20%
	Net value savings: €4.2 million (based on average B-stock price of €210)
	Loss reduction: €190,000
Net material savings: 2,920 tons (average 146 kg per WM-TD unit)	
Achieve low error rate in value recovery of returned appliances	
Lower time to provide product information	

To enable sharing of product/component condition information with different partners

Table 16 represents the mapping of Business Objectives of LEX to the measurements mentioned in the DOA.

Table 16: Mapping business objectives of LEX to measurements mentioned in DOA

Business objective	KPIs mentioned in the DOA
Collect and Analyze Printer Usage Data	
Optimization of Reverse Logistics Based on Printer Usage Data	Reduce reverse logistics cost
Increase Number of Returned Non-MPS Printers	Increase the portfolio of returned used non-MPS printers
Increase RLC Utilization Capacities	Reduce sorting and testing costs
	Reduce per unit reverse logistics costs
Increase Usage of Secondary Spare Parts and Optimize New Printer Production Spare Parts	Increase social acceptance of remanufactured printers and cartridges through awareness program
Increase Cartridge Returns for Non-MPS Printers	

Table 17 represents the mapping of Business Objectives of CECO to the measurements mentioned in the DOA.

Table 17: Mapping business objectives of C-ECO to measurements mentioned in DOA

Business Objective	Measurements promised in DOA
Improve data integration	Increase the offer of relevant products and used spare parts in the right quality by 30% annually.
Increase data transparency for remanufacturing	Create portals for at least 2 different user-groups
Increase data transparency for customers	
Increase predictability of the remanufacturers' supply-demand planning	
Increase core returns	1 million additional used spare parts accessible for remanufacturing in Europe (Calculated for Automotive Remanufacturing Industry).
	Generate €20 million worth of value for value chain actors.
	Net material saving: 6000 tons (avg. used part weight 6KG)
Reduce sorting errors	Apply AR-support in sorting-process in at least 1 of C-ECO's location and collect user-feedback
	Reduce sorting-errors by 20%
Enable proactive error prevention	
Reduce effort for training operators	
Reduce time needed to prepare reports	
Decrease the number of support cases	
Enable reporting scalability	Net CO ₂ saving: 4500 tons CO ₂ -eqv (avg. CO ₂ saving 4.5 kg/part)
Attract customers outside the automotive sector	